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Impact Factor: 0.98

E-ACCOUNTING: CHALLENGES & FUTURE

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ABSTRACT

A business requires that one keeps close control of its financial data. When your financial data is in the office and you aren't, how do you retrieve the information you need? The solution is simple, and it's called E-Accounting. E-Accounting helps to keep financial data and accounting applications in a safe, secure environment. Access can, however, be provided to permitted users regardless of their location. New technologies, like the Internet and mobile solutions, have provided new business opportunities and operations. E-Accounting is new development in field of accounting. In e-accounting, source documents and accounting records exist in digital form instead of on paper. E-accounting concept is adopted at international level. E-accounting helps businesses keep their financial data and accounting software in a safe, secure environment, allowing real time access to authorized users, irrespective of their location or computing platform. Therefore this paper is based on review of the problems & prospects about e-accounting and provides a brief outline about adoption and impact of e-accounting. Concept and features of e-accounting, e-accounting challenges & security issues have been discussed in the paper comprehensively.

Key words: e-accounting, financial data, adoption, security issues, challenges.

Introduction

E-Accounting might just be the beginning of a new era where world would be extending its arms to India with perspective that "India is the place which can deliver the best".

Accounting plays a critical role in the success or failure of contemporary business institutions. Accounting systems are responsible for recording, analyzing, monitoring and evaluating the financial condition of companies, preparation of documents necessary for tax purposes, providing information support to many other organizational functions, and so on. Prior to the advent of personal computers, businesses were limited to manual methods for keeping track of financial data. According to Tavakolian (1995), the manual accounting systems consisted of paper ledgers, typewriters and calculators. Typewriters were used to type invoices and cheques, and all calculations were performed using calculators. However, with this system it was possible for errors to be introduced into the data since they could go undetected for quite some time. Like many other industries, the accounting industry changed with the arrival of personal computers. A computerized accounting system is able to handle financial data efficiently, but the true value of an accounting system was that it was able to generate immediate reports regarding the company. E-Accounting refers to Electronic Accounting, a term used to describe an accounting system that relies on computer technology for capturing and processing financial data in organizations. Bodnar and Hopwood (2001:411, 426-427) use concepts like *on-line input systems*, *on-line real-time processing* and *on-line reporting* and state as follows:

"In paperless input systems transactions are input directly into the computer network, and the need for keying in source documents is eliminated."

The Accounting Act of 1997 and further guidelines issued by the Accounting Board in 2000 provide an institutional setting for the use of electronic data media in financial accounting for registering, transferring and storing data as well as reporting information electronically. Thus, source documents and accounting records exist in digital form instead of on paper in an electronic accounting system. There has been a constant growth in the use of information and communication technology in business to support the exchange of data and

information within and between organizations. New technologies, like the Internet and mobile solutions, have provided new business opportunities and operations. According to IFAC (2002:1) e-business is believed to have a significant impact also on accounting systems, through changing business processes. The introduction of the internet has revolutionized the process of business automation. Revolution is all about transformation for the good.

Objective of the Study

The objective of research article is to find out the importance, challenges and future prospective of E-Accounting in India.

Meaning & Concept of E-Accounting

E-Accounting is new development in field of accounting. In an electronic accounting system, source documents and accounting records exist in digital form instead of on paper. E-Accounting might just be the beginning of a new era where world would be extending its arms to India with perspective that "India is the place which can deliver the best". So e-Accounting has visited India with a rainbow of opportunities.

E-accounting involves performing regular accounting functions, accounting research and the accounting training and education through various computer based /internet based accounting tools such as: digital tool kits, various internet resources, international web-based materials, institute and company databases which are internet based, web links, internet based accounting software and electronic financial spreadsheet tools to provide efficient decision making. This discussion implies that e-accounting can also be viewed as online accounting.

E-accounting has also bring global opportunities in the field of business as its easier and less time consuming to do business globally by using electronic data transfer and communication. The introduction of the Internet has revolutionized the process of business automation. Revolution is all about transformation for the good. Outsourcing, in this sense, has grown in necessity and has gained a prominence in boardroom meetings. The evolution of technology made what was unthinkable, possible. Welcome the revolution!

It means all your transactions will record in online server or data base, just like website or blog or web blog. But for opening or making accounts will uses login id and password. In E-Accounting the accountant and employer both feel satisfaction because, this is cheap and without software defaults or failure. Your accounts saves in online server or database, so there is no need to record manually. By this way we can save large amount of money spending on manual books and different accounting software. But for using e-accounting we should learn it first, because without learning of E- Accounting, you never expert in E-Accounting. Almost all companies uses same system of online accounting but some advance companies makes own system of their online or E-Accounting. They need only those dedicated person who know Internet and computer well, without this they cannot appoint any E-Accountant. E-Accounting Concept is adopted international level. The International Accounting Standards Board is also in favors of E-Accounting. It is developing new standards which can be utilized for E-Accounting at international level. The International Federation of Accountants is searching all the tools of E-Accounting for quality accounting education and its development. There are long list of international accounting organizations that is supporting E-Accounting. We can include in this list The UK's Financial Reporting Review Panel , The UK and Irish Auditing Practices Board , American Accounting Association (AAA) , Association of Chartered Certified Accountants , Accounting Education foundation of Nova Scotia , Foundation for Accounting Education . All major accounting relating to General ledger Book keeping and maintenance , Bank reconciliation MIS Cash management , Account Payable and Receivables , Billing Payroll , Budgeting Management of Records Asset , management Detailed financial analysis , Collection management , Credit management , Generation of financial reports Financial statements are totally online . Company's entire accounting project can be easily outsourced by E-Accounting system.

Features of E-Accounting:

E-accounting can be recognized by the following characteristics which all make for a much more efficient accounting process.

1. Multi-user access
2. Multi-site access
3. A single / multiple, shared database(s)
4. Zero system administration for end-users
5. Very economical to provide service to large number of clients
6. Enhancements and fixes continuously developed and installed by service provider

E-Accounting Adoption Model:

Hart and Saunders have developed e-accounting model, explaining impact of e-accounting. They identified four factors - perceived benefits, organizational readiness, external pressures and trust - as the main reasons that could explain the e-accounting adoption behavior of small firms and the expected impact of the technology. Of these factors, external pressure and organizational readiness were considerably more important than perceived benefits and trust. Their model is as below.

- Perceived benefits refer to the level of recognition of the relative advantage that e-accounting technology can provide the organization.
- Organizational readiness refers to the level of financial and technological resources of the firm. Further, financial readiness refers to financial resources available to pay for installation costs, implementation of any subsequent enhancements, and ongoing expenses during usage, whereas technological readiness is concerned with the level of sophistication of IT usage and IT management in an organization.
- External pressure to adopt refers to influences from the organizational environment. The two main sources of external pressure to adopt are competitive pressure and the imposition by trading partners. As more competitors and trading partners become e-accounting capable, small firms are more inclined to adopt e-accounting in order to maintain their own competitive position.

- Trust is mainly considered as openness and reliability. Openness may, for example, mean willingness to share rather than withhold information and thus improve the efficiency of the partners' operations. Reliability may concern transmission of accurate data and information between the partners.

E-accounting impact refers to the actual benefits adopters receive from utilizing e-accounting. It is assumed that the level of integration of e-accounting is positively related to the benefits an adopter can receive. Usually, the adoption of e-accounting requires coordination between at least two organizations, the relationship between the organization and its prospective trading partner(s). According to the Accounting Board (2000) the use of e-accounting will lead to a more efficient and reliable accounting as well as reduce the costs of accounting.

Importance of E-accounting

In a fast paced world, the clients need to have control over financial data to know their 24x7 financial positions, from any geographic locale. In this regard, main benefits of e-accounting can be listed as below.

- E-Accounting helps businesses keep their financial data & accounting software in a safe, secure environment, allowing real time access to authorized users, irrespective of their location or computing platform.
- This is possible due to an Application Software hosted on a remote but safe and secure environment by and ASP (Application Service Provider) that allows access to users of financial information with different levels of permission and password.
- One can send paper documents through an e-fax or by scanning and e-mailing it. Once we receive the scanned image of the document, the transaction is posted in Accounting.
- No need of in-house bookkeepers' training and expertise
- No problems with employee turnover, vacations, sick leave and absenteeism
- No communication difficulties between the accountant and business owner or organization due to load / work pressure.
- The business organization can concentrate on the revenue side of business, and spend as little time as necessary on the accounting and payroll function.
- The accounting function receives attention only when a critical need arises. No time wastage.
- No Payroll related costs, FICA, workers compensation, unemployment, vacation/sick benefits, health insurance benefits, and many other expenses.
- Cost saving on office space (rent for additional offices)
- Save time and money, the cost is low (in some cases: free).
- Gain greater control of finances by moving from paper records to computerized accounting software.
- Transactions that affect the company's bank account can be sent automatically to the online accounting application.
- They are portable. The company can access its documents from almost any computer with a broadband connection.
- If the company's computer crashes, its documents are still safe on the server.

Uses of E-Accounting

- There are more than thinkable uses of computers for accounting purposes. For management accounting purpose or for that matter if you are running a company, you need to know exactly whether you are on schedule. That can be done if the accounts are in computers.
- For banks, it helps like anything in interest calculation, provision for doubtful debts, writing off of debts, etc.
- For police, the use of computers means that data pertaining to all account holders in banks now can be collected and analyzed very quickly. So if police want to know if anyone has assets above his disclosed income, then they can do so far too quickly.

- Records (entries in accounts) can be kept for any amount of time in electronic format. Floods in 2005 in Mumbai showed that paper can be destroyed far too quickly. But electronic details cannot be destroyed that quickly and can be kept very safe.
- For share trading, after introduction of computers, anyone from anywhere in world can access his demat account and put trade. This has helped in channelizing household savings to capital market. And records for that too can be kept for any amount of time.
- For data entry level, the accuracy can be monitored quite properly. Errors of commission and omission can be caught fairly easily.
- Complicated calculations of computing minority interest in mergers/takeovers, calculation of NAV of mutual fund units, up to date position in derivatives segment, profit or loss in equity/derivatives/commodities/forex etc., can be done easily.
- Since computerization, all banks have started central processing of financial transactions like clearing and settlements. This means anywhere banking for you. You can deposit funds at one city and travel to another city and withdraw funds from there. No need to actually carry physical cash.
- Since computerization, credit cards have come in existence. And that too are used this extensively. By use of computers, international clearing has become far too quick.
- For making tax return preparation, compliance reporting, bank account reconciliation, financial write-up and reporting etc.

Problems in E-Accounting

Data security — All the data of the company resides on a remote server: however, a backup can be taken regularly.

Speed — Most of the currently available online office suites require a high broadband Internet connection.

Lacks some features available on the offline office suites: but this is progressively becoming available. A network connection (usually Internet access) is required to send and receive changes. That is, internet dependence makes it more difficult to work offline.

From above criticisms, it can be said that today, where information can be compromised and distributed, global firms need to be cent-percent assured that their information is safe and are being safeguarded from identity theft. Being professionals, Indian Chartered Accountants should be absolutely confident about the work process, ensure service integrity, observe professional ethics and generate trust and confidence in the client for striking a lasting business relationship.

Benefit/ Cost Analysis of E-Accounting

The costs and benefits of e-accounting are presented below (Deshmukh, 2006:10-11):

Benefits:

- Faster cycle times – these include credit approvals, payments and collections, posting of transactions, closing of the books, generation of records and more time available for higher-level analysis
- Continuous service availability, 24/7 access, and more satisfied internal and external customers
- Reduced error rates- that means fewer transactions with errors as well as fewer errors
- Reduced accounting staff and improved productivity
- Better cash management – efficient payments and effective collections
- Cost saving in mail, paper and storage of paper
- Improved audit trails and security.

Costs:

- Investment required in computers hardware and software

- Initial need for expensive consultants
- Cost involved in systems, processes, processing of information and report generation changes
- Continual training and retraining needs and/or requirements personnel with specialized skills
- User resistance
- Careful attention needs to be paid to security, control and audit requirements for financial transactions during the initial configurations. If the initial configuration of the system is not correct or the integration with ERP software or legacy systems is faulty, then there are recurring costs and fewer benefits from the implementation.

Role of E-Accounting for Economic Development

As an unavoidable result of the new technologies like the internet and mobile solutions, new business opportunities and operations emerge. Nowadays, the economy has information and communication technologies, which entails the development of e-accounting. The term “e-accounting” or “digital accounting” refers to the application of technologies related with online/internet to the both public and private sector accounting implementations.

- New technologies, like the Internet and mobile solutions, have provided new business opportunities and operations.
- According to IFAC (2002:1) e-business is believed to have a significant impact also on accounting systems, through changing business processes and the evidence available to support business transactions, and leading to changes in the accounting records maintained and the accounting procedures followed (Gullkvist, 2003:536). The accounting profession must be able to deliver good, reliable and timely measurements of both the results of operations and the health of the companies 156 *European Journal of Economics, Finance And Administrative Sciences - Issue 38 (2011)* involved in affiliations to interested stakeholders in both summary and detailed data as desired by the information users.
- To make the information produced and provided in the electronic accounting information system more reliable, electronic accounting principles were developed by the International Federation of Accountants (IFAC). These principles, including accounting information security and accounting information process principles can be observed by the two groups in the table below. (IFAC, 2002:9–11).
- In E-Accounting the accountant and employer both feel satisfaction because, this is cheap and without software defaults or failure. Your accounts saves in online server or database, so there is no need to record manually. By this way we can save large amount of money spending on manual books and different accounting software.

E-Accounting Principles	
Accounting Information Security Principles	Accounting Information Process Principles
Integrity	Completeness
Availability	Accuracy
Confidentiality	Timeliness
Authenticity	Assessability
Authorization	Order
Non-repudiation	Inalterability

Source: IFAC, 2002, “E-Business and the Accountant: Risk Management for Accounting Systems in an E-Business Environment”, 9-11.

Challenges of E-Accounting

E-commerce is rapidly transforming the way accounting and auditing functions are performed, posing new challenges to the accounting profession. Electronic commerce has also increased the complexity of transactions

as they are being increasingly done among parties who have never met. In such an environment, it is important to have an assurance about the quality and reliability of trading partners, financial viability of companies, data security, reliability of systems and many such issues.

Website Development Costs: Development of a website is the first step in the direction of e-commerce. It would engage organizational resources for planning, infrastructure built-up, hardware acquisition, software tools, domain registration, as well as graphics and content development.

Cost of Operating a Website: Once the website development is complete, the operating stage begins where one has to address to issues such as personnel training, data backup, creating linkages, monitoring “hits,” continuous updating, etc.

Security Threat: Internet security is a broad term that refers to the various steps individuals and companies take to protect computers or computer networks that are connected to the Internet. One of the basic truths behind Internet security is that the Internet itself is not a secure environment. The Internet was originally conceived as an open, loosely linked computer network that would facilitate the free exchange of ideas and information. Data sent over the Internet—from personal e-mail messages to online shopping orders—travel through an ever-changing series of computers and network links. As a result, unscrupulous hackers and scam artists have ample opportunities to intercept and change the information. It would be virtually impossible to secure every computer connected to the Internet around the world, so there will likely always be weak links in the chain of data exchange.

Viruses: Well-known causes of computer problems are viruses, or damaging programs that are introduced to computers or networks. Some viruses rewrite coding to make software programs unusable, while others scramble or destroy data. Many viruses spread quickly and operate subtly, so they may not be noticed until the damage has already been done.

Hackers: Hackers may hack password and attempt to over-whelm the system with information from the outside so that it shut down.

Another common method of attack used by hackers is e-mail spoofing. This method involves sending authorized users of a computer network fraudulent e-mail that appears as if it were sent by someone else, most likely a customer or someone else the user would know. Then the hacker tries to trick the user into divulging his or her password or other company secrets. Finally, some hackers manage to shut down business computer systems with denial of service attacks. These attacks involve bombarding a company's Internet site with thousands of messages so that no legitimate messages can get in or out.

One of the most effective ways to protect a computer network that is connected to the Internet from unauthorized outside access is a firewall. A firewall is a hardware security device that is installed between a computer network and the Internet. It acts like a Web server, routing traffic, but also blocks external users from accessing the internal computer system. Of course, a firewall cannot protect information once it leaves the network. A common method of preventing third parties from capturing data while it is being transmitted over the Internet is encryption. Encryption programs put data into a scrambled form that cannot be read without a key.

Threats to Accounting Information Systems

Threats to accounting information systems come from a variety of sources. If ignored, they can destroy the relevance and reliability of financial information, leading to poor decisions by various stakeholders. At the point of data collection, it is important to establish security controls that ensure that transaction or event data are valid, complete, and free from material errors. Threats to accounting information systems can also occur during the data processing phase. Creating illegal programs, accessing or deleting files, destroying or corrupting a program's logic through viruses, or altering a program's logic to cause the application to process data incorrectly all represent threats. Threats to database management might include unauthorized access that allows

altering, deleting, corrupting, destroying, or stealing data. The failure to maintain backup files or other retrieval techniques represents a potentially devastating loss of data. Threats to the information generation and reporting phase must also be considered. For example, the theft, misdirection, or misuse of computer output could damage the competitiveness or reputation of the organization.

Future of E-Accounting

How the Internet will affect accounting

Accounting evolution will depend on developments in the Internet and electronic commerce. Accountants will have to use technology to record, analyze and forecast business activity in an online real-time mode.

- **Enhanced and changed disclosures**

The ease of electronic publishing and the ubiquitous nature its display will tempt organization to move from traditional reports to Web published reports. These will first resemble their paper counterparts and then evolve towards the real use of the medium.

- **Broader and Deeper Financial Disclosure**

Investors are aware that firms have vast quantities of continuously updated on-line information and that cost of electronic disclosure is decreasing exponentially. Investors will require not only more detailed and timely disclosures but also for permanent on-line link to certain intranet sectors. Consequently we should see an increase in the scope and frequency of financial disclosure.

- **Tax Accounting**

The federal government and local government are important constituencies of business. Internet technology is likely to increase the reliance of tax authorities on on-line interactive tax audits. The cost of specific audits will decrease, thereby permitting to audit more businesses more frequently and more intensely. Increasingly sophisticated on-line expert systems in tax accounting are likely to proliferate. Taxpayers and tax accountants may have to be more careful, meticulous, and alert. Likewise, on-line interactive audit technology will enable governments to audit more comprehensively and frequently business compliance with a host of laws and regulations which will create a more challenging environment for business and government accountants alike.

- **Remote Computer-Based Accounting Services**

Remote tax consulting services, remote bookkeeping, remote financial statement preparation, remote auditing, and continuous auditing processes are progressively emerging as realistic services that may even make a profit. The scope and nature of these services, initially mainly a mutation of traditional services, are rapidly evolving.

- **Goodbye to Ledgers and T-Accounts, Hello to Data based Accounting**

Ledgers, T-accounts and paper-based journals are an anachronism. Computer-based packages are now integrated databases using distributed relational database systems to create views of the performance and management of a corporation. Relational Database products (such as Oracle and Ingres) are progressively the base for a larger and larger percentage of financial applications, often segmented by organizational unit.

- **Interactive Distance Auditing**

Private accountants for companies and investors will have to design, administer, control, and audit much more complex information networks born out of a variety of Internet - intranet fusion patterns. Public accountants will have to modify their assurance procedures to allow for more information being disclosed with greater speed and frequency.

The Internet will allow for greater reliance on interactive distance auditing. With exceptions for physical inspection of assets, Internet technology will make physical proximity and personal presence in auditing much less important. On-line access to materials, and remote transfer and retrieval of documents, will be enhanced by audio and video capabilities. This will make distance auditing via the Internet fully interactive.

Costs of specific audit tasks will be significantly reduced. At the same time the variety, scope and frequency of on-line distance auditing will grow. A large portion of on-line auditing will become continuous.

Continuous on-line distance auditing over the Internet is bound to increase opportunities for more timely detection of serious lapses in financial reporting and financial performance. Commensurably, obligations and legal liability of auditors will undergo substantial changes. Auditors will have to be much more alert and timely in their reporting, recommendations and certification.

Conclusion

E-Accounting has visited India with a rainbow of opportunities. This also makes us show the world our compatibility with any environment where we can deliver positive output under any situation. If time and money for getting a job done is the issue for the globe today, then why not let it be done by skilled experts who can do it at the best of their professional excellence.

The introduction of the internet has revolutionized the process of business automation. E-accounting or online accounting is new development in field of accounting. E-accounting has visited India with a rainbow of opportunities. E-accounting is the application of online and internet technologies to the business accounting function. In e-accounting, source documents and accounting records exist in digital form instead of on paper. All major institution and organization at national and international level are in the favors of e-accounting. Perceived benefits, organizational readiness, external pressures and trust are the main factors that could explain the e-accounting adoption behavior of small firms and the expected impact of the technology. E-accounting helps businesses keep their financial data and accounting software in a safe, secure environment, allowing real time access to authorized users, irrespective of their location or computing platform and offers a number of benefits. Though, data security, speed of broadband internet connection, network connectivity etc. are the basic problems related with e-accounting. Accountants, being information providers, are natural agents and users for information technologies. In an environment of continuous contact with customers, electronic care, and continuously changing costs and benefits new roles and activities are emerging. In a computer environment that will link many processes, intelligent agents performing many functions, deskbound and distributed, monitoring features will emerge to facilitate accounting practice and enable online auditing. Risks and exposures, particularly of intrusion and viruses, will present new challenges to accountants. Broader and deeper financial statements, with drill downs and user based presentation, will push the limits of the current standards and acceptable practices.

Managers, as well as accountants, will have to get used to this environment and adapt their practices to a new world.

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